

Parental Involvement and Numerical Competence of Grade Three Learners: Basis for School Initiated Numeracy Program

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Abstract. This study aims to determine what school-initiated numeracy program can be developed and designed for the grade three learners in Sulop District, Davao Del Sur Division. A total of 74 public school teachers are the respondents were identified through stratified random sampling technique and five (5) of the participants was purposively selected for the in-depth interview. The study utilized a n input-process-output design. After the quantitative data analysis, the level of parental involvement in terms of emotional support, communication with teacher, and financial support was moderate and was sometimes evident. On the other hand, the level of numerical competence of learners garnered an overall fairly satisfactory performance, Moreover, the significant influence of parental involvement on the numerical competence of the grade 3 learners, the results showed that none of the domains significantly influence the numerical competence of the learners and this leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. In addition, the output or school initiated program to enhance numeracy competence based on the assessments were generated from the responses of the participants namely: (1) Support Seeking Systems, (2) Math Homework Lab, and (3) Family Math Nights.

KEY WORDS

1. Parental involvement 2. numerical competence 3. emotional support

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1. Introduction

Numerical competence is crucial from an early age, and establishing strong numeracy skills in elementary school students is foundational for their academic and lifelong success. The significance of fostering numerical competence in young students encompasses several key areas: cognitive development, academic performance, and future educational prospects. Mathematics is an essential subject at all educational levels, including university, as proficient individuals utilize fundamental mathematics in daily life. Nevertheless, the majority of children in the country continue to struggle with maths

proficiency.

Furthermore, Grade 3 students in the Philippines have historically scored low in national assessments for mathematics. The National Achievement Test (NAT) results have consistently shown that a significant portion of students in the early grades struggle with basic numeracy skills. For instance, the Department of Education (DepEd) reported that the mean percentage score for mathematics at the elementary level often falls below proficient levels, indicating widespread difficulties in basic numerical competence (DepEd, 2021).

In line with this national trend, Sulop Central Elementary School, located in the Sulop District under the Division of Davao del Sur, has also observed concerning performance among its Grade 3 learners. A majority of these students have demonstrated significant challenges in attaining grade-level numerical competence. Based on the 2023 Rapid Mathematics Assessment (RMA) report from the school's Management Information System (MIS), most Grade 3 learners scored below 75

The study sought to address the following objectives: a.) to determine the level of parental involvement in terms of emotional support, communication with teachers, and financial support. b.) to determine the level of numerical competence of learners in terms of number sense and counting, place value understanding, manipulation of arithmetic operations, a basic understanding of fractions and decimals, and measurement and data interpretation. c.) to determine the domain of parental involvement that significantly influences numerical competence of learners, and d.) to propose and design an school-initiated numeracy program based on the results of the assessment from the study.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) None of the domains of parental involvement significantly influence

numerical competence of learners.

The results and findings of this study are valuable to various stakeholders. For the Department of Education, they inform curriculum development, guide teacher training, and support efficient resource allocation to enhance numeracy education. School heads gain insights into students' skills, enabling targeted interventions and better resource management. Teachers can use the findings to tailor instruction, address learning gaps, and improve student outcomes. Learners benefit from focused programs that strengthen mathematical understanding and confidence, while parents are empowered to support learning at home more effectively. Lastly, future researchers can build on this study to explore new interventions and refine strategies in mathematics education.

Figure 1 illustrates the flow of the study. This study follows the input-process-output method where the input of the survey is the Parental Involvement and the Numerical Competence of Grade Three learners. The process is through assessment using test-type questionnaire, an assessment tool designed for evaluating the foundational mathematical skills of learners in Grades 1 to 3, and the expected output is the School Initiated Numeracy Program for Grade Three Learners.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a mixed-method Explanatory Sequential approach, beginning with the collection and analysis of quantitative data on parental involvement (emotional support, teacher communication, financial support) and learners' numerical competence (number sense, arithmetic operations, data interpretation), followed by qualitative interviews to further explain the re-

sults (Creswell Plano Clark, 2018). Guided by the Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model, the study used descriptive and inferential analyses to identify which domain of parental involvement significantly influenced numerical competence among Grade Three learners. Findings informed the development of a school-based numeracy program aimed at addressing gaps and enhancing parental engagement.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—The researcher strictly followed the ethical standards set by RMC’s Research Ethics, ensuring social value, informed consent, participant safety, and transparency throughout the study. Focusing on the influence of parental involvement on the numerical competence of Grade Three learners in Sulop District, the research underscored the benefits for students, teachers, and school leaders while minimizing risks. Ethical measures included obtaining dual consent from both parents and child participants, safeguarding confidentiality under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, addressing participants’ vulnerability, and ensuring voluntary participation without coercion. The researcher, qualified through postgraduate training and expert consultation, utilized adequate facilities and upheld justice by treating all participants equitably, offering tokens of appreciation, and allowing withdrawal at any time. No conflict of interest was present, and findings were transparently communicated through appropriate channels to ensure validity, reliability, and broader educational impact.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The researcher strictly followed the ethical standards set by RMC’s Research Ethics, ensuring social value, informed consent, participant safety, and transparency throughout the study. Focus-

ing on the influence of parental involvement on the numerical competence of Grade Three learners in Sulop District, the research underscored the benefits for students, teachers, and school leaders while minimizing risks. Ethical measures included obtaining dual consent from both parents and child participants, safeguarding confidentiality under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, addressing participants’ vulnerability, and ensuring voluntary participation without coercion. The researcher, qualified through postgraduate training and expert consultation, utilized adequate facilities and upheld justice by treating all participants equitably, offering tokens of appreciation, and allowing withdrawal at any time. No conflict of interest was present, and findings were transparently communicated through appropriate channels to ensure validity, reliability, and broader educational impact.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—To collect quantitative data, the researcher used an adapted survey questionnaire, including the Parental Involvement Questionnaire from Cariaga et al. (2023) which measured emotional support, communication with teachers, and financial support is sometimes evident. Its reliability, confirmed by a Cronbach’s alpha of .827, indicated strong internal consistency. Meanwhile, a researcher-developed 30-item test assessed Grade 3 learn-

ers' numerical competence in terms of number sense and counting, place value understanding, manipulation of arithmetic operations, a basic understanding of fractions and decimals, and measurement and data interpretation, with items validated by experts and analyzed using the Discrimination and Difficulty Indices. Mean gain scores were interpreted using DepEd Order

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The study's quantitative phase involved several steps to ensure accurate data collection, starting with formal permission from academic and schools division authorities, followed by coordination with school heads for survey distribution. The research instruments underwent content validation by experts and pilot testing for reliability, with items analyzed using the Discrimination and Difficulty Indices. Surveys were distributed and retrieved in person, encouraging genuine

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used to address the research questions: Mean was utilized to assess the levels of parental involvement and learners' numerical competence across various domains. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis identified which do-

No. 08, s. 2015. For the qualitative phase, a validated interview guide explored participants' views on a school-initiated program to enhance numerical skills, with data accuracy ensured through expert panel validation, audio recording review, and follow-up communication with participants.

responses and safeguarding data integrity. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS to identify patterns and correlations. For the qualitative phase, expert-validated interview guides were used in one-on-one, face-to-face interviews conducted in a confidential setting, with responses recorded (with consent) and transcribed accurately. Data from interviews were analyzed using thematic content analysis, supported by triangulation and member checking to ensure credibility, minimize bias, and strengthen findings.

main of parental involvement significantly influenced learners' numerical competence. For the qualitative phase, Thematic Content Analysis was employed to examine interview transcripts and identify key themes related to participants' experiences.

3. Results and Discussion

This section highlighted the results and discussion of the study. The presentation starts from the descriptive analysis of parental involvement and numerical competence of learners followed by the discussion on the significant influence of parental involvement towards numerical competence. The presentation ends with the discussion on what school initiated program can be developed to enhance numerical competence of the learners.

3.1. Level of Parental Involvement —Table 1 shows the summary of the level of parental involvement in the three categories, namely the emotional support, communication with teacher, and financial support. Between the three parental involvement categories, the parental involvement in terms of emotional sup-

port got the highest category mean of 3.34 described as moderate followed by financial support with a category mean of 3.16 described as moderate, indicating that parental insolvent on learners in terms of emotional support and financial support are sometimes evident. Meanwhile, communication with teachers got the least cate-

gory mean of 3.09 also described as moderate indicating that the parental involvement in terms of communication with teachers was sometimes evident. The overall mean rating on this domain marked (3.20) which was described as moder-

ate. This means that the summary of the level of parental involvement in the three categories, namely emotional support, communication with teacher, and financial support was sometimes evident.

Table 1. Level of Parental Involvement

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Emotional Support	3.34	Moderate
2	Communication with Teacher	3.09	Moderate
3	Financial Support	3.16	Moderate
Overall		3.20	Moderate

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High

3.2. Level of Numerical Competence of Learners—Table 2 presented the level of numerical competence among Grade Three learners, revealing an overall mean score of 0.79, which falls under the Fairly Satisfactory category. This suggests that while learners shows basic numerical competency, the learners struggles with consistency and needs reinforcement in applying concepts accurately. Among the specific indicators, Measurement and Data Interpretation (0.89) received the highest rating, classified as Very Satisfactory, indicating a relatively strong performance in this area. Conversely,

Place Value Understanding (0.73) was rated Did Not Meet Expectations, highlighting a critical gap in learners’ comprehension of numerical structures. The remaining indicators—Number Sense and Counting (0.75) and Manipulation of Arithmetic Operations (0.79)—were both categorized as Fairly Satisfactory, while Basic Understanding of Fractions and Decimals (0.80) was rated Satisfactory. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions, particularly in Place Value Understanding, to strengthen learners’ overall numerical competence and build a more solid mathematical foundation.

3.3. Domains of Parental Involvement that Significantly Influence Numerical Competence of learners—Table 3 exemplified the regression test among parental involvement namely: emotional support, communication with teachers, and financial support towards numerical competence of learners. The overall correlation had a computed r-value of 0.31 with a p-value of .000 in the significant level denotes the moderate positive correlation (Cohen, 2002) between

the two variables with which the hypothesis on significant relationship was tested.

The findings indicate a moderate significant relationship between the parental involvement and numerical competence of learners. The analysis yields an F-value of 2.453 with a p-value of ; .070, indicating a moderate but not statistically significant relationship at the 0.05 level. This suggests that while parental involvement may influence numerical compe-

Table 2. Level of Numerical Competence of Learners

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Number Sense and Counting	0.75	Fairly Satisfactory
2	Place Value Understanding	0.73	Did Not Meet Expectations
3	Manipulation of Arithmetic Operations	0.79	Fairly Satisfactory
4	Basic Understanding of Fractions and Decimals	0.80	Satisfactory
5	Measurement and Data Interpretation	0.89	Very Satisfactory
Overall		0.79	Fairly Satisfactory

Legend: .75 below: Did Not Meet Expectations, .76–.79: Fairly Satisfactory, .80–.84:

Satisfactory, .85–.89: Very Satisfactory, .90–1.00: Outstanding

tence, the evidence is not strong enough to confirm a definitive effect. Additionally, the R² value of 0.094 indicates that 9.4 of the variance in learners’ numerical competence is explained by the predictors, while the remaining 90.6 is influenced by other factors not accounted for

in the three dimensions under study. This suggests that although the predictors contribute to numerical competence, a significant portion of variability is driven by external or unexamined influences.

Table 3. Domains of Parental Involvement that Significantly Influence Numerical Competence of Learners

Parental Involvement	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision@=0.05
Constant	0.479	0.127	—	3.784	0.000	
Emotional Support	0.004	0.047	0.013	0.085	0.933	(Accept Ho)
Communication with Teachers	-0.009	0.040	-0.033	-0.223	0.824	(Accept Ho)
Financial Support	0.097	0.052	0.317	1.843	0.070	(Accept Ho)

Dependent Variable: Numerical Competence of learners

R = 0.31 R² = 0.094 F-ratio = 2.453 p-value = 0.000

Regression coefficients reveal that not all domains of parental involvement significantly influence the numerical competence of learners. Among the three domains, none had a statistically significant impact. Financial Support had

the highest standardized coefficient (= 0.097) but a p-value of .070, which exceeds the 0.05 significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for this domain. Similarly, Emotional Support (p = .933) and Communi-

Fig. 2. School Initiated Program to Enhance Numerical Competence

cation with Teachers ($p = .824$) did not show significant effects, indicating that these areas do not directly contribute to numerical competence in a statistically meaningful way.

The p -value of .000 for the constant term suggests that numerical competence is influenced by other factors beyond the three domains of parental involvement examined in this study. However, further analysis of the regression coefficients confirms that none of the domains—Financial Support ($p = .070$), Emotional Support ($p = .933$), and Communication with Teachers ($p = .824$)—significantly influence numerical competence. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis across all domains.

3.4. School Initiated Program to Enhance Numerical Competence of Grade 3 Learners—In response to the results of the assessment, which revealed that Grade 3 learners demonstrated an overall numerical competence score of 0.79, classified as Fairly Satisfactory, a school-initiated intervention was developed with the aim of addressing the specific gaps identified in key areas of mathematical learning. Particularly, learners exhibited strong performance in Measurement and Data Interpretation

(0.89 - Very Satisfactory) but struggled significantly in Place Value Understanding (0.73 - Did Not Meet Expectations). Other indicators such as Number Sense and Counting (0.75), Manipulation of Arithmetic Operations (0.79), and Basic Understanding of Fractions and Decimals (0.80) fell within the Fairly Satisfactory to Satisfactory range. These results suggest that while learners possess basic numerical skills, there is a clear need for consistent reinforcement, remediation, and family engagement to ensure mastery of foundational concepts.

To address these gaps, the following three-part intervention will be implemented through a structured and strategic process, with each component designed to meet both the cognitive and emotional learning needs of students, while also strengthening home-school collaboration:

Figure 2 shows the school initiated program to enhance numerical competence of the Grade 3 learners. Three (3) themes were generated from the responses of the participants namely: (1) Support Seeking Systems, (2) Math Homework Lab, and (3) Family Math Nights. The results showed based on the participants responses were derived from their experiences, coping mechanism, and insights.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement of the grade 3 learners in terms of emotional support, communication with teachers, and financial support. Followed by

the discussion of the level of numerical competence of learners in terms of number sense and counting, place value understanding, manipulation of arithmetic operations, basic understanding of fractions and decimals, and measurement and data interpretation. Further, to determine the significant influence of parental involvement towards numerical competence. The presentation ends with the discussion on what school initiated program can be developed to enhance numerical competence of the learners. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—On the level of parental involvement findings suggest that parental involvement in emotional support moderately influences learners' educational experiences, though its consistency varies. Many parents offer strong encouragement and comfort, but overall emotional support is moderate. This variability underscores the need for nurturing environments to help children thrive academically and emotionally. Additionally, the findings suggest a need for programs that assist parents in delivering more consistent emotional support, particularly in families facing financial or social challenges.

On the level of parental involvement in terms of communication with teacher it was found that parents are relatively engaged in their child's education through occasional contact with teachers, attendance at school events, and support for educational programs. However, the study also reveals that factors such as communication and limited access to school meetings may influence the extent of parental involvement. Therefore, enhancing opportunities for communication, both formal and informal, and addressing barriers to participation could improve parental engagement and further support student achievement.

On the level of parental involvement in terms of financial support the results underscore that parental financial involvement plays a moderate yet essential role in students' educational success. While parents generally manage to provide for their children's school needs, there is an indication that more support could enhance the academic experiences of students, especially in families facing economic difficulties.

On the level of numerical competence of learners the findings indicate that while Grade Three learners exhibit basic numerical competence, there are inconsistencies in their ability to apply mathematical concepts accurately. Strengths were observed in measurement and data interpretation, but significant challenges remain in place value understanding, which did not meet expectations. Other areas, such as number sense, counting, arithmetic operations, and fractions and decimals, showed fairly satisfactory to satisfactory performance. These results highlight the need for targeted instructional support, particularly in foundational numerical concepts, to enhance learners' overall mathematical proficiency.

On the significant influence of parental involvement, particularly emotional support, on the numerical competence of Grade Three learners. The findings indicate that none of the examined domains of parental involvement—financial support, emotional support, and communication with teachers—had a statistically significant impact on learners' numerical competence. While parental involvement remains essential in education, these results suggest that other factors, such as instructional methods, curriculum effectiveness, and student engagement in mathematics, may play a more critical role in developing numerical skills. This highlights the need for a more comprehensive approach to improving numerical competence beyond parental support alone.

4.2. Conclusions—On the school-initiated program aimed at enhancing the numerical competence of Grade Three learners has been structured around three key themes: Support Se ek-

ing Systems, Math Homework Lab, and Family Math Nights. These themes highlight the importance of creating a supportive environment that encourages collaboration among students, families, and educators. By implementing these initiatives, the school can foster a more engaging and effective approach to improving students' numerical skills

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that the Department of Education promote parental involvement, especially in providing emotional sup-

port. School heads should initiate family-school projects, while teachers foster inclusive environments and maintain communication with parents. The SGC is urged to lead numeracy programs, and the PTA should organize capacity-building and engagement activities. Parents must support learning at home, and learners should take responsibility for their progress. Future research should explore other factors affecting numerical competence, such as teaching strategies, socioeconomic status, and peer influence.

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